

Integration of regulatory constraints from a policy database into the energy system modeling tool atlite

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MOTIVATION

- Need to drastically scale wind energy installation to meet climate targets
 - 2% of Germany's land area by 2032, with 115 GW in 2030 [1]
- Legislation and public acceptance play an important role in wind turbine deployment [2], [3]
- Necessary to effectively model not only technical but regulatory constraints

LEGISLATIVE DATABASE

- NFDI4Energy Task Area "Integrating Society and Policy in Energy Research" collated the database *Landscape and environmental regulation for energy production and infrastructure* [4] because there is a lack of machine-readable regulatory data for energy modeling and policy analyses
 - Legislative regulations for wind turbine installation (here mainly using setback distances)
 - Scope for this analysis: Germany, Greece, and France

IMPLEMENTING REGULATORY CONSTRAINTS IN ATLITE

- Open-source Python software package atlite converts historical weather data and land-use restrictions to power generation potentials and time series [5]
- Cutouts (2020 ERA-5 [6]) used for historical weather data
- Comparison between PyPSA-Eur default configuration [7] and modelled database regulatory constraints

	Included land types	Setback distances/conditions				
		Residential (CLC [8])	Motorways (OSM [9])	Airports (OSM [9])	Coast	Natural Areas (Natura2000 [10])
Default PyPSA-Eur (All)	Based on CLC grid codes [8]: specific kinds of agricultural, forest and semi natural land	1000m	CLC, 1000m	-	-	Excluded
Germany Database		State dependent (up to 1000m)	40m	Excluded with 1000m	-	
Greece Database		1000m	Within maximum distance for repair (region dependent)	-	100m	
France Database		500m	100m	-	100m	300m

LAND ELIGIBILITY FOR DEFAULT PYPSA-EUR CONFIGURATION AND DATABASE REGULATIONS

REFERENCES

[1] Federal Ministry of Justice. (2023). Renewable Energy Sources Act.

[2] Lehmann, P., Reutter, F., Tafarte, P. (2023). Optimal siting of onshore wind turbines: Local disamenities matter. *Resource and Energy Economics* 74, 101386.

[3] Reitz, S., Goshen, L., Ohlhorst, D. (2022). Trade-offs in German wind energy expansion: building bridges between different interests, values and priorities. *Energy, Sustainability and Society* 12 (39).

[4] Chaianong, A., Milioritsas, I., Malhotra, P., Günkördü, D., Weiß, J., Weko, S., Lilliestam, J. (2025). Data on landscape and environmental regulations for energy production and infrastructure (Version 1, February 2025). Sustainability Transition Policy Group, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg.

[5] Hofmann, F., Hampp, J., Neumann, F., Brown, T., Hörsch, J. (2021). Atlite: A Lightweight Python Package for Calculating Renewable Power Potentials and Time Series. *Journal of Open Source Software* 6(629, 3294).

[6] Munoz Sabater, J. (2019). ERA5-land hourly data from 1950 to present.

[7] Brown, T., Hörsch, J., Hofmann, F., Neumann, F., Victoria, M., Zeyen, L. (2025). Configuration – PyPSA-Eur. [Readthedocs.io](https://pypsa-eur.readthedocs.io/en/latest/configuration.html#atlite).

[8] European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2018). CORINE Land Cover (raster 100 m), Europe, 6-yearly.

[9] OpenStreetMap contributors. (2025). Open Street Maps (Germany, Greece, France Latest). <https://www.openstreetmap.org>.

[10] European Environment Agency. (2022). Natura2000 (vector data).

[11] European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Elsner, P., Collaer, J., Uihlein, A. (2025) The Onshore Wind Potential of the EU and Neighbouring Countries, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/1638274>, JRC139999.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 501865131.